

AspirE

Asian prospects
in (re)migration
to/within the EU

Second report on the impact of dissemination strategies

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ABBREVIATIONS

CD&E = Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan

DPO = Data Protection Officer

EC = European Commission

ECRs = Early Career Researchers

EP = European Parliament

EU = European Union

EUHK = The Education University of Hong Kong

GA = Grant Agreement

GUF = Goethe University Frankfurt

HE = Horizon Europe

Iscte = University Institute of Lisbon

IS-VASS = Institute of Sociology-Vietnam Academy of Social Sciences

MAU = Mahidol University

MS = Member States

MU = Masaryk University

PI = Principal Investigator

REA = Research Executive Agency

SMC = Scalabrini Migration Center

TAU = Tampere University

ULB = Université libre de Bruxelles

UMIL = University of Milan

VAPEC = Vietnam Asia-Pacific Economic Center

WP = Work Package

WUT = Waseda University

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present document is the second report on the impact of AspirE's dissemination strategies. As the first report published in December 2023, this document aims to provide an overview of the effectiveness of AspirE's Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (CD&E) Plan to reach both academic and non-academic public. It describes AspirE's main dissemination strategies (publications and presentations) and major communication tools' impact (website, podcasts, social media) during the project's first two years.

Keywords

communication, dissemination, report, X (formerly Twitter), Facebook, Matomo, AspirE

1. INTRODUCTION

AspirE is a REA-funded project that examines the decision making of aspiring (re)migrants in 11 countries across Asia and Europe. One of the many milestones associated to AspirE is a yearly report on the impact of the project's dissemination strategies on the circulation of information about AspirE's activities and research results.

Dissemination strategies are integral to the CD&E Plan (see Figure 1 below) and designed to maximise the project's scientific and societal impact. These strategies are directed toward the following key audiences: the international scientific community involved in migration studies across disciplines such as sociology, anthropology, law, geography, and psychology; European policymakers at both the European Union (EU) and Member State (MS) levels; aspiring Asian economic migrant communities; Asian NGOs addressing migration-related challenges; European and Asian (post-)graduate students; and informed, engaged citizens.

Figure 1. AspirE's Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan

As AspirE is completing its second year, data collection related to empirical work packages is almost over. This document will provide a non-exhaustive list of activities achieved thus far and evaluate the effectiveness of the various communication tools employed by AspirE to enhance the visibility of its activities, including the project's website and its social media accounts (X and Facebook).

It must be emphasised that this report is focused on what has been planned, which the AspirE consortium has been pursuing since its beginning on 1 January 2023. Changes in initial strategies may occur as the project advances and an updated report will be provided in month 36.

2. DISSEMINATION STRATEGIES

In the context of EU-funded research, dissemination involves sharing knowledge and research findings with a broad audience, including scientists, authorities, policymakers, relevant sectors, and the general public. AspirE employs two primary dissemination strategies: open-access publications and presentations. While certain dissemination activities focusing on the project as a whole and its outcomes are scheduled for a later phase, this section highlights the ongoing efforts.

2.1. Open-access publications

AspirE team members are encouraged to publish in open access. In order to track team members' publications, an internal strategy has been put in place via a Google form to collect all the necessary information, which is further shared via AspirE's website, social media accounts, and its bimonthly Newsletter. Here is a list of AspirE's publications since the beginning of the project¹:

- **“Humanising research on (non-)migration decision-making: a situated framework”**: This essay written by Asuncion Fresnoza-Flot (AspirE's main PI) was submitted on the Open Research Europe (ORE) platform, which is “an open access publishing venue for European Commission-funded researchers across all disciplines, with no author fees” (see <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu>). For its first version (September 2023), the essay received 2 reviews: approval and approval with reservations. For its second version (February 2024), the essay received 1 review: approved with reservations. This essay seeks to advance the conceptual understanding of transnational migration by exploring the factors driving individuals' aspirations or intentions to (re)migrate and the reasons behind their decision to remain in their current location. This publication is central to the AspirE project, as it strives to offer nuanced perspectives that humanise research on (non-)migration decision-making processes.
- **“The bitter business of berries”**: This four-part story written by the Isaan Record² (NGO based in Thailand) in December 2023 and published on its website in English (<https://theisaanrecord.co/2023/12/13/the-bitter-business-of-berries-part-i-berries-hold-promise-to-unburden-generations-of-thai-debt/>) highlights the struggles of one couple from Isaan who travelled to Finland to pick berries. Burdened by significant debt, the couple was encouraged by local government agencies and the Ministry of Labour, who promised that berry picking could be a lucrative opportunity, allowing low-income families to earn a substantial amount within a few months. However, upon arrival in Finland, they encountered harsh living and working conditions and inadequate pay and returned home with little to show for their efforts. The story follows the couple as they endure a bitter experience amidst the promise of sweet berries. The Isaan Record received honourable mentions for outstanding media awards from two prestigious institutions for this publication. The first was awarded by the Issara Amantakul Foundation, an organisation dedicated to promoting freedom of the press in Thailand. The second came from Amnesty International Thailand in recognition of their report on the labour exploitation of Thai berry pickers in Finland, who faced unfair wages and, in some cases, fell victim to human trafficking. The Isaan Record simultaneously published this story in Thai (<https://theisaanrecord.co/2023/10/31/jenpreeya-jampeehom-bloody-berry/>) but in a long one piece format without dividing the story into four parts.

¹ The publications listed are also available on AspirE's website: <https://aspire.ulb.be/impact/publications>

² The official name of this NGO is “Foundation for Isaan Education and Popular Media”. However, the present report refers to this NGO as “The Isaan Record”, the name used in its website and social media accounts.

- **“Eettinen ennakkoarviointi kansainvälisen tutkimushankkeen koetinkivenä”** (Ethical review as the first challenge in a large international research consortium): Mitra Härkönen (postdoctoral researcher) and Mari Korpela (PI) of AspirE’s Finland-based team published this article on AntroBlogi in April 2024, a Finnish independent blog. The article explores the ethical review process in a large EU Horizon-funded research project, where one must navigate and reconcile various ethical evaluation procedures and practices across different countries.
- **“Luonnonmarjojen ylirajainen poliittinen talous”** (The transnational political economy of wild berries): In May 2024, Minna Seikkula, a postdoctoral researcher based in Tampere University (Finland), published an essay examining the international mobility associated with the Finnish wild berry industry. In her work, she emphasises the importance of adopting a translocal perspective in both academic research and political decision-making, one that considers the conditions in both the countries of origin and destination.
- **“Routledge Handbook of the Vietnamese Diaspora – Vietnamese migrants in the Czech Republic: Busy entrepreneurs and their children”**: In May 2024, Adéla Souralová, PI of the Czech Republic team based in Masaryk University, published a book chapter in Routledge Handbooks dedicated to the migration from Vietnam to the Czech Republic.
- **“The Thai Berry Pickers in Finland”**: Kwanchanok Jaisuekun based at Mahidol University published an essay (in Thai) in the Prachakorn (a blog affiliated to the Institute for Population and Social research from Mahidol University) shedding light on the phenomenon of Thai berry pickers, highlighting the vulnerability of Thai labour in the Finnish berry industry. These Thai seasonal workers are not protected by Finnish labour laws due to their non-employee status.
- **“Verso una nuova apertura alle migrazioni per motivi di lavoro in Italia? Intermediazione, rischio di frode e limbo legale nella lotteria del decreto flussi”** (Towards a new opening to labour migration in Italy? Brokering, risk of fraud and legal-status limbo in the lottery of the 'flow decrees'): Fabio de Blasis (postdoctoral researcher) and Paola Bonizzoni (PI) of the AspirE’s team based in the University of Milan published an article in Italian and presented it during the *6th Convegno Mondì Migranti* in Milan in May 2024. They presented it also in June 2024 during a press conference at the Senate of the Italian Republic. After this event, the Italian government implemented changes to its labour migration policy to curb abuses and exploitation of migrant workers.
- **“Socio-Legal production of the tourist-seasonal labourer for the Finnish berry industry”**: In May 2024, Minna Seikkula, postdoctoral researcher based in Tampere University (Finland), contributed to the issue “The Global Disappearance of Decent Work? Precarity, Exploitation, and Work-Based Harms in the Neoliberal Era” as part of the (In)Justice International Collective. This publication is fully open access.
- **“Migration from Vietnam to the EU: policies, channels and characteristics”**: The AspirE’s IS-VASS team published an article in the Vietnam Journal of Sociology to examine how Vietnamese migration to six selected EU countries has been shaped by visa policies and national laws, highlighting trends, policy gaps, and the need for improved migration management.
- **“Blood berries: Thai government finally moves on human trafficking of wild berry workers in Finland and Sweden... after 14 years”**: The Isaan Record shared an article published on its

website to report on a 14-year-old court case related to a company alleged of trafficking Thai workers picking wild berries in Finland and Sweden.

- **“Three ways in which EU mobility policies and their implementation treat Asians unequally”:** Asuncion Fresnoza-Flot (PI of the AspirE project) was invited to publish a Research Short on the platform of Migration to Research Policy Co-Lab of the INNOVATE project (a Horizon Europe-funded coordination project). Her piece was published in November 2024.
- **“Quando a guadagnarci non sono solo gli scafisti”** (When it's not just smugglers who profit): Article published by Unimil Team on NaspRead - the brainchild of Nasp, the most important social and political science network in Northern Italy.

At the moment, the AspirE consortium is working on four publication projects: two special issues and two edited volumes focusing on the results of WP2 and WP3. Its first Special Issue project has been accepted by an international peer-reviewed journal in the field of migration studies and will be presenting the key findings from the project’s WP2 expert interviews. Its second Special Issue project will be proposed to another international peer-reviewed journal before March 2025; it will be showcasing the results of the project’s WP3 semi-structured interviews with aspiring (re)migrants. Regarding its edited book projects, AspirE will submit to an international publisher in migration studies two volume proposals: one on the results of its WP2 policy content analysis (to be proposed in February 2025) and the other on the findings of its WP3 social network map analysis (to be proposed in April 2025).

2.2 Presentations

Based on Figure 1, presentations encompass different types of activities: conferences, EU and country reports, webinars, policy briefs, innovation laboratory, comic book, roundtable discussions, photo exhibit, and advocacy report, among others. Only few, explained below, can be covered at this stage of the project.

CONFERENCES

AspirE team members are encouraged and expected to present findings in international conferences, which is one of the many milestones associated to the project. Here is a non-exhaustive list of conferences in which AspirE team members participated to share their research findings³:

Date	Event	Presentation title	Participants
November 2023	6 th China-Europe Research Platform on Chinese Migration to and Beyond Europe (CERPE) Workshop Hosted by the ISCTE – University Institute of Lisbon	"Reluctant exiles always? Or shrewd opportunists? Hong Kong immigrants to Europe under Chinese rule"	The Education University of Hong Kong (EUHK) team
March 2024	Viiikki Sustainability Research Seminar, “Potential	“Thai berry pickers, seasonal work, and the Finnish sustainable food systems”	Tampere University (TAU) team

³ Please note that these events have been presented as “News” on AspirE’s website: <https://aspire.ulb.be/news>

	<p>Sustainability Impacts of Migration”</p> <p>Hosted by Finnish Environment Institute (SYKE), Natural Resources Institute Finland (Luke), and the Helsinki Institute of Sustainability Science (HELSUS)</p>		
May 2024	<p>Mondi Migranti 6th Conference</p> <p>“Importatori riluttanti, esportatori di confini: le politiche migratorie tra necessità economiche e retoriche ostili”</p> <p>Hosted by University of Milan (UMIL)</p>	<p>“Verso una nuova apertura? Intermediazione, rischio di frode e limbo legale nella lotteria del decreto flussi” (Towards a new opening to labour migration in Italy? Brokering, risk of fraud and legal-status limbo in the lottery of the 'flow decrees')</p>	University of Milan (UMIL) team
June 2024	<p>Robert Schuman Centre: joint Sessions of Workshops</p> <p>“Ethical dilemmas in migration and citizenship policies: characteristics, variations, causes and responses”</p> <p>Hosted by European University Institute</p>	<p>“Immigration regimes, strategies of navigation, and ethical dilemmas among legal-administrative intermediaries in Italy”</p>	UMIL team
July 2024	<p>IMISCOE 21st Annual Conference – “Migration as a social construction – a reflexive turn”</p> <p>Hosted by the ISCTE – University Institute of Lisbon</p>	<p>Workshop on “Mobility policies and migration decision-making: exploring their possible link(s) through researchers’ reflexivity”</p>	AspirE and its sister-projects (DYNAMIG and PACES)
		<p>Panel on “(Re)constructing the diasporic experiences of Hong Kong migrants in Asia: a relational approach”</p>	EUHK team
		<p>Panel on “Constructed desirability of the EU as mobility destination from</p>	AspirE teams: Université libre

	Asia: perspectives of social actors 'here' and 'there'"	de Bruxelles (ULB), Scalabrini Migration Center (SMC), UMIL, Mahidol University (MaU), TAU, EUHK, University Institute of Lisbon (Iscte), Waseda University (WU), and Goethe University Frankfurt (GUF)
	Panel on "Moulding categories, accessing rights: migrants and intermediaries"	UMIL team
	Panel on "Assembling mobilities: culture, industry and migration between Japan and Europe"	AspirE teams: WU and GUF
	Panel on "Model minority or threat? Vietnamese migrants in the Czech Republic and Vietnam"	Masaryk University (MU) team
	Panel on "Escaping gendered expectations of the home society: settling practices of Japanese skilled women in Germany"	GUF team
"Past, present, and future of Philippine labor migration: 50 years and beyond"	"Europe on their minds: (re)migration aspirations of Filipino youth"	SMC team
Hosted by the Philippine Migration Research Network (PMRN) and Philippine Social Science Council (PSSC)		
IOM Consultation Workshop on Viet Nam 2023 Migration Profile Report	"Situation of Vietnamese citizens migrating to Europe"	AspirE teams: Vietnam Academy of Social Sciences (IS-VASS) and Vietnam Asia

	Hosted by the Consular Department, Ministry. of Foreign Affairs in Vietnam		Pacific Economic Center (VAPEC)
	13th conference of the European Association for Southeast Asian Studies (EuroSEAS) conference Hosted by the University of Amsterdam	The panel “Aspirations to migrate to the EU: A comparative perspective from Southeast and East Asian countries” which included the following papers: “Fleeing from a Sinking Japan: Recent Tendencies of Japanese Lifestyle Migrants to Europe” “Aspirations to migrate to the EU: How have Vietnam citizens aspired and decided to migrate?” “Lifestyle aspirations of Chinese migrants in Portugal: a threefold temporal approach analysis” “Gender Dynamics and Migration Patterns: Exploring East and Southeast Asian Migrants’ Experiences in Belgium” “Driving forces of highly-skilled Japanese to migrate to Germany”	AspirE teams: ULB, WU, IS-VASS, Iscte, and GUF
	The 18 th European Association of Social Anthropologists Biennial Conference Hosted by the University of Barcelona	“Wild berry and mushroom picking and the lived experiences of Thai migrants in Finland”	TAU team
August 2024	The European Association for Chinese Studies (EACS) 25th Biennial Conference Hosted by Tallinn University	"The role of air pollution in the decision-making migration process of wealthy citizens from China to Portugal"	Iscte team
	16th European Sociological Association (ESA)	“Mobility aspirations amongst youth of Chinese, Brazilian, and Ukrainian origin in Portugal”	Iscte team

	<p>Conference – “Tension, Trust and Transformation”</p> <p>Hosted by the European Sociological Association in different locations in Porto</p>		
	<p>The 22nd Nordic Migration Research Conference</p> <p>Hosted by the University of Bergen</p>	<p>TAU team co-hosted a panel “Rural migrations and precarity: from lived experience to policy making” and presented the following papers:</p> <p>“Journey of hope or journey of despair: unpacking the lived experiences of Thai berry pickers in Finland”</p> <p>“Migration for the sake of lively rural regions? The case of wild berry industry related mobility”</p>	<p>TAU team and the University of Helsinki</p>
September 2024	<p>“Berry pickers, transnational human trafficking, and the future of Thai workers’ welfare”</p> <p>Hosted by The Isaan Record</p>	<p>The Isaan Record hosted a panel at the hotel of Khon Kaen University (Thailand) on Thai workers’ welfare, focusing on the exploitation of berry pickers abroad</p>	<p>The Isaan Record team</p>
	<p>“Supporting Evidence-Based Policy and Programmes in the Context of Cross-Border Mobility in Viet Nam” workshop</p> <p>Hosted by the Consular Department of Ministry of Foreign Affairs</p>	<p>Invitation to participate and present the AspirE project and the social network mapping done within the framework of the project</p>	<p>AspirE team: IS-VASS and VAPEC</p>
October 2024	<p>Global Mobility Humanities Conference (GMHC) – “Mobilities, aspirations and affective futures”</p>	<p>“Im/mobility aspirations of Japanese migrants in urban Germany in intersectional perspective”</p>	<p>GUF team</p>

	Hosted by the Konkuk University in Seoul		
November 2024	7th China-Europe Research Platform on Chinese Migration to and Beyond Europe (CERPE) – Chinese Immigrants in Europe: Living in Transnationality and Transculturality Hosted by the Xiamen University in China	"Managing disappointment: comparing pre- and post-arrival migration imaginaries of Chinese in Portugal"	Iscte team

EU AND COUNTRY REPORTS – POLICY BRIEFS

AspirE produced and published an EU mobility policies report in collaboration with the Centre for European Policy Studies (CEPS), a Brussels-based Think Tank organisation. The report (downloaded 72 times) focused on the following matters: labour migration, tourism, family reunification, student migration, investment migration, and the EU’s freedom of movement. CEPS also published a separate report on humanising EU migration policy on its website (downloaded 290 times). Additionally, six MS country reports on mobility frameworks and five country reports on socio-legal framework of human spatial mobility across the five Asian countries involved in the project were published on the project website (downloaded 675 times in total). The country-specific analysis results have been separately and comparatively assessed to determine whether the same set of policies at the EU level apply, and whether these policies have the same impact across different national and local contexts.

These reports served as the basis of AspirE’s first set of policy briefs: “A critical appraisal of the EU’s regular migration system. Objectifying, structurally discriminatory and not aligned with EU and international standards” (downloaded 327 times); and “Critical gaps in the implementation of EU and selected Member States’ policies on migrating from Asia to the European Union” (downloaded 49 times). They were also the basis of AspirE’s Research Short essay entitled “Three ways in which EU mobility policies and their implementation treat Asians unequally” published on the website of INNOVATE’s Migration to Research Policy Co-Lab.

WEBINARS

AspirE aims to organise three Webinars summarising the insights drawn from each stage of the project’s data-collection and analysis. Webinar 1, entitled “Aspiring (re-)migrants behaviour in mobility policies”, took place on 29 and 30 January 2024 and drew from the project’s WP2 on the socio-legal context of migration decision-making. UMIL (WP2 coordinator) with the help of the ULB (see Annex 1) organised this event. Webinar 2 named “Micro- and meso-level drivers of (re)migration”, led by the ULB, drew from the insights of WP3 on the individual motivations driving migration decisions. ULB organised it on 30 September (see Annex 2). Finally, Webinar 3 entitled “Temporality of (re)migration decisions” will take place in April 2025 and will draw from the project’s WP4 that is oriented towards understanding the temporality of decision-making. Iscte (WP4 coordinator) will organise the webinar with the help of the ULB.

OTHER EVENTS

AspirE participated and was featured in a series of other activities. Below is a non-exhaustive list:

Nature of the event	Date	Description	Participants
Collaborations with sister-projects	11 April 2023	Participation in the Consortium meeting of DYNAMIG to present the AspirE project	ULB team
	23 June 2023	AspirE organised a meeting gathering representatives of DYNAMIG and PACES to brainstorm on future joint collaboration	ULB team
	19 September 2024	AspirE's PI joined onsite the DYNAMIG consortium meeting in Florence to discuss several pathways to impact (dissemination, outreach, cooperation with sister-projects)	ULB team
	18 December 2024	AspirE, DYNAMIG, and PACES coordinated the publication of 3 digital interviews with project research participants on International Migrants Day	ULB team
Activities with Embassies, Ombudsman offices and more.	06 October 2023	Finland-based PI welcomed the Ambassador of Thailand to Finland and received a research report on Thai berry workers in the country	TAU team
	13 September 2024	Finland-based PI participated in a roundtable discussion at the Royal Thai Embassy in Helsinki.	TAU team
	10 October 2024	The Czech team presented the results	MU team

		from their analysis of Czech migration policies and interviews with migration experts at the Ombudman's office	
Activities with the European Commission	14 December 2023	AspirE participated in the Migration to Policy roundtable "Bridging Research and Policy" to present the project, some of its preliminary findings, and recommendations to the Commission	AspirE teams: ULB and UMIL
Media cooperation	20 November 2023	The Isaan Record produced a documentary entitled "Bloody Berry" on YouTube and shared it via Facebook. The Thai version on the latter platform accumulated 6,300 views while the English one was viewed 238 times	The Isaan Record team
	23 February 2024	EUHK-based team was featured in Ming Pao (Hong Kong newspaper) to present some preliminary findings on the trends of Chinese aspiring (re)migrants in Europe	EUHK team
	27 February 2024	AspirE's main PI was interviewed and featured in Ming Pao	AspirE teams: ULB and EUHK
	01 March 2024	EUHK team appeared on Ming Pao newspaper to share the procedures faced by Chinese migrants in the migration application process to Europe	EUHK team

	27 March 2024	The AspirE project was presented (in Cantonese) to the audience of the Hong Kong radio programme “Clear Day Breakfast”	EUHK team
	30 May 2024	The UMIL team participated in a press conference organised at the Italian Senate to present their report on the labour migration policy in Italy known as “decreto flussi”	UMIL team
	28 June 2024	Project members met the artists Benoit+Bo during their exhibition	AspirE teams: ULB and Iscte
	05 September 2024	Research by TAU team was featured in the prominent weekly news magazine Suomen Kuvalehti	TAU team
	30 September 2024	The VAPEC team produced a migration policy brief related to the AspirE project on the website of the Asia-Pacific Economic Review	VAPEC team
	05 October 2024	The Isaan Record produced a documentary entitled “The Berries Blues” on YouTube and shared it via Facebook. The Thai version on the latter platform accumulated 63,000 views while the English one was viewed 171 times	The Isaan Record team
Screenings	15-29 February 2024	The AspirE team based in Iscte organised 3 3 cinema sessions “Ways of Seeing China”	Iscte team

	24 April 2024	The AspirE team based in Iscte was involved in the organisation of the film screening “The Way of the Shaman Drum” followed by a roundtable discussion chaired by Iscte PI	Iscte team
	11 November 2024	The documentary “The Berries Blues” produced by the Isaan Record was screened in Helsinki, followed by a panel discussion featuring a Thai workers’ rights activist, an AspirE postdoctoral researcher, and representatives of the berry pickers	AspirE teams: The Isaan Record and TAU
Award winning	16 February 2024	The Isaan Record received a “Honorable Mention” from Amnesty International Thailand’s media award for their work on the situation of Thai berry pickers abroad	The Isaan Record team
	15 March 2024	The Isaan Record website received an honourable mention from the Issara Amantakul Media Awards (a Thai Journalistic Association) for its online media on the 4-part story “The bitter business of berries”	The Isaan Record team
	July 2024	The SMC received the second prize for its poster highlighting their findings on semi-structured interviews with Filipino migrants	SMC team

Celebrations	10 February 2024	The Iscte team participated in the celebration of the new year of Dragon in Lisbon. A news post and photos were published on the project website	Iscte team
	25 March 2024	VAPEC co-organised an event in the occasion of the Social Work Day in Viet Nam with the aim of promoting labour migration	VAPEC team

UPCOMING ACTIVITIES

As per the Grant Agreement, a series of mostly public activities are planned for the third and final year of the project:

Date in 2025	Activity description	Participants
January	Open data training online	To be organised by MU for the AspirE consortium and potentially for a wider audience
February	Steering Committee meeting in Hong Kong	All AspirE team members
March (initially scheduled in May)	Innovation Laboratory	To be co-organised by CEPS, a Think Tank based in Brussels
April	Webinar 3 on WP4 findings	To be organised by Iscte in the collaboration with all AspirE team members
May	/	/
June	Toolbox for migration agents and NGO members drawing from AspirE's Innovation Laboratory	ULB's responsibility
	Comic book manuscript submission for publication	ULB's responsibility
July	Training curricula for early career researchers	MU's responsibility The curricula will be published on AspirE's website and further

		disseminated to reach early-career researchers
August	/	/
September	Local policy roundtable discussions will take place in Asia and Europe	To be organised by all local teams
October	An onsite and online exhibition of AspirE's selected findings will be organised. Additionally, AspirE is planning a one-day workshop to launch the exhibition (papers and roundtable discussions)	To be organised by Iscte with the help of the ULB. The event will be open and free of charge to the public
	Publication of the third set of policy briefs drawing from WP4 findings	To be prepared by ULB in collaboration with Iscte
November	An advocacy report will be published	ULB's responsibility
	Project's final conference in Brussels	ULB's responsibility with the collaboration of all AspirE teams
	Publication of the last set of AspirE's podcast highlighting WP3 and WP4 findings	ULB's responsibility with the collaboration of all AspirE teams
December	Report on the dissemination of policy briefs	ULB's responsibility with the collaboration of all AspirE teams
	Third report on the impact of dissemination strategies	ULB's responsibility with the collaboration of all AspirE teams

Additional activities that do not appear on the Grant Agreement include:

- Conferences and workshops: AspirE plans to maintain its active participation in international conferences. In February 2025, EUHK team will organise a workshop in Hong Kong by to present the findings of AspirE's social network map analysis. AspirE proposed a panel in the upcoming IMISCOE conference in July 2025; the result of this proposal will come out in January 2025. AspirE will also co-organise with its sister projects (DYNAMIG and PACES) a policy event in November to share with policymakers and grand public the results of these projects' studies.

- Early Career Researchers' (ECR) online Seminar Series: From February to June 2025, AspirE's ECRs will be organising a seminar series aiming to present some findings from their respective studies under the project and engage in dialogues with invited discussants and other participants. The Seminar Series will be coordinated by two ECR representatives.
- Special Issues: AspirE plans to publish 3 Special Issues highlighting the findings of its empirical Work Packages (WP2, WP3, and WP4) respectively. So far, one focusing on WP2 migration expert interviews has been accepted by an international peer-reviewed journal on migration. Another Special Issue is under preparation and will focus on WP3 interview results. It will be submitted to another international peer-reviewed journal on migration. The third Special Issue project that will focus on WP4 findings is work in progress.
- Edited volumes: AspirE is also planning to publish 4 edited volumes: first on policy content analysis (WP2), second on the findings of the project's social network map analysis (WP3), third on WP4 findings, and last one will be on the project's overall results based on cross-analysis of the following datasets: semi-structured interviews, social network mapping, and video diaries.

3. COMMUNICATION TOOLS

It is essential to explore the various communication tools established to disseminate AspirE's activities and findings to a broader audience. This section will analyse how these tools contribute to effectively achieving this objective.

3.1. AspirE's website

AspirE communicates its activities and research results on its website, which was created in May 2023 (see <https://aspire.ulb.be>). It is the most resourceful tool for information on the AspirE project, its objectives and methodology, Work Packages, team members and advisors, and its different communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities.

As outlined in the CD&E plan, AspirE's website is hosted on the ULB institutional web platform, ensuring long-term durability and protection against piracy. The website was developed by the agency "Typi Design" in collaboration with AspirE's project manager and the principal investigator. The designs featured on the website were created using Canva, for which AspirE holds a three-year subscription. The site includes the following sections: Home, Research, Team, News, Impact, and Contact (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Upper menu bar of the project's website

In relation to the cookie setup, the project utilises Matomo (which means "honesty" in Japanese) to gather statistical data on website visits. This open-source analytics platform prioritises user data protection, ownership, and privacy. As a result, all collected data remains anonymous, is not shared with third parties, and is securely hosted on ULB servers.

Figure 4. Visitor map worldwide (19/12/2023)

Figure 5. Visitor map worldwide (19/12/2024)

The website of AspirE has attracted a global audience, with most visitors originating from Europe. However, its reach extends across all continents, demonstrating the project's international impact and visibility. The AspirE website has experienced remarkable growth in its audience over the past year, with a steady increase in the number of visits over time. Figures 4 and 5 illustrate the more than threefold increase, highlighting growing interest and engagement with the project and underscoring its expanding reach and impact across diverse audiences. Visitors access the website through various channels, such as direct searches, referral links, and social media platforms. Matomo, the analytics tool used by the project, offers detailed insights into how users find and interact with the website, as depicted in Figure 6. These analytics include data on traffic sources, popular content, and user behaviour, which help the project team optimise the website's accessibility and relevance.

Figure 6. Channel types through which the project’s website was found (19/12/2024)

CHANNEL TYPE	▼ VISITS	ACTIONS	ACTIONS PER VISIT	AVG. TIME ON WEBSITE	BOUNCE RATE
Direct Entry	5,166	17,453	3.4	3 min 28s	45%
+ Search Engines	1,933	5,611	2.9	2 min 14s	50%
+ Social Networks	1,243	3,619	2.9	2 min 25s	50%
+ Websites	489	1,720	3.5	3 min 14s	46%
+ Campaigns	16	35	2.2	2 min 5s	38%

3.2. Podcasts

In order to share research findings to a wider audience, AspirE intends to produce three sets of podcast series . As of December 2024, two sets of podcast have been uploaded in the [AspirE website](#), on [SoundCloud](#) and [Spotify](#), as well on [ULB’s website](#).

FIRST SET OF PODCAST

The first series of podcasts, consisting of seven episodes, was published on AspirE’s website between October and December 2023, aiming to introduce the project to a broader audience. The inaugural episode provides an overview of AspirE, with the project’s main PI, Asuncion Fresnoza-Flot, explaining its scope, research questions, objectives, methodologies, organisational structure, and anticipated outcomes in a concise 15-minute segment. Episodes 2 to 7 delve into specific migration corridors between Europe and Asia, featuring insights from local PIs and AspirE researchers:

- Thailand-Finland migration case study
- Philippines-Italy migration case study
- Japan-Germany migration case study
- Vietnam-Czech Republic migration case study
- China-Portugal migration case study
- Asian immigration to Belgium case study

This podcast series provides an in-depth exploration of significant migration patterns and research insights across various countries. However, reaching a broad audience for a scientific podcast can be challenging. On SoundCloud, AspirE’s first podcast series has been played between 2 and 51 times, while on Spotify, the series garnered 37 listens.µ

SECOND SET OF PODCAST

AspirE’s second podcast series was published in October 2024. Episodes 1 to 4 provide a comprehensive overview of the key findings from Work Package 2, which focused on policy content analysis and interviews with migration experts. These episodes delve into the insights gained from examining migration policies and perspectives from professionals in the field, shedding light on the current migration landscape in Europe. The final episode features a discussion with Anjum Shabbir, representing the Centre for European Policy Studies (CEPS), and Asuncion Fresnoza-Flot, the project's lead Principal Investigator. In this episode, they share a series of policy recommendations to foster a more humane and inclusive approach to regular migration within the EU. Their recommendations are directed at both EU-level policymakers and national governments, emphasising the need for migration policies that prioritise human dignity, equity, and respect for migrants’ rights. This episode aims to inspire positive change by suggesting practical, evidence-based solutions for improving the treatment of migrants across Europe. Due to financial limitations, this podcast series was only uploaded on Spotify where the series has been played 15 times.

These modest numbers reflect common barriers in engaging audiences with academic content. Such challenges may include: the niche topic associated to AspirE's podcast because scientific podcasts often cater to specialised audiences which limits broader appeal ; lack of visibility due to limited targeted promotion which complicates the ability to reach listeners who may benefit from the content; limited audience awareness can also be a consequence of the challenges mentioned because many people interested in the topic may not know about the existence of such podcast; and platform preferences as the platforms chosen for the AspirE podcast may not align with the habits of the target audience.

To address these issues and increase engagement, based on feedback received during the project review at the European Commission, several strategies can be employed:

- Enhanced promotion: To raise awareness, actively promote the podcast on social media, academic networks, and partner websites.
- Collaborations: Partner with other projects, institutions, or influencers in the field of migration studies to reach their audiences.
- Content adaptation: Create shorter, engaging clips or infographics highlighting key insights to attract attention and direct listeners to the full episodes.
- Audience interaction: Host live Q&A sessions, discussions, or webinars related to the podcast topics to foster a sense of community and draw in listeners.
- Cross-platform availability: Ensure the podcast is accessible on multiple platforms, including those popular in specific regions of interest.

By implementing these strategies, the project can expand its reach and effectively engage a larger audience with its valuable research findings. For instance, the ULB has ensured to have AspirE podcast featured on ULB's podcast webpage (see <https://actus.ulb.be/fr/ulb-medias/ulb-podcasts/aspire-le-podcast-qui-explore-les-dynamiques-de-la-remigration-entre-lasie-et-leurope>).

THIRD SET OF PODCAST

The third and last set of podcasts will be published on the project's website in November 2025. Similar to the first and second set of podcasts, this series will contain several episodes. While the planning might be subject to change, the first episode aims to bring the results of WP4's video diaries collection to the fore. The second episode will be about the results of WP4's group discussions. The final episode will explain the project's findings and revisit its research questions and objectives.

3.3. Social media presence

AspirE is active on two social media platforms: X (formerly Twitter) and Facebook. To evaluate and enhance the impact of the AspirE project, a comprehensive social media publication plan was developed. This plan details the project's presence on social media platforms, specifically X (formerly Twitter) and Facebook, and outlines a structured approach for content distribution and engagement. It specifies the types of content to be shared across these platforms, including research updates, event announcements, and key findings. In addition, the plan identifies accounts to follow on X and pages to like or follow on Facebook, which are aligned with the project's research focus and target audience. The strategic use of visual materials is emphasised to capture attention and increase engagement. Hashtags relevant to migration and research are also incorporated to increase discoverability and join larger conversations within the field. The plan specifies a consistent posting frequency, with a target of at least three weekly posts, to maintain an active presence on both platforms.

Since the project’s social media accounts have been consistently active, the visibility and reach of the project can now be quantitatively measured. Using the data collected through tools like the Publication and Communication Google Forms, which were introduced earlier in the report, the project team has been able to track engagement metrics and assess the effectiveness of their social media strategy. Furthermore, a social media calendar was created to ensure that the accounts are regularly updated, with a clear schedule for posting content and engaging with the audience. This calendar serves as a key tool for maintaining a steady flow of communication, ensuring the project’s visibility and connection with its audience over time.

X (formerly Twitter)

AspirE’s account on X follows the same logic as the Facebook page based on the social media calendar. All information shared passes through both channels, usually on the same day.

Figure 7. Number of followers on X (19/12/2024)

As of December 2024, the total number of posts amounts to 184. The performance of the account was regularly monitored until June 2024, when X restricted analytics access to free accounts, making it available only to those subscribed to X Premium or Premium+ plans. The following statistics were created with temporary Hootsuite free trial version and cover the period of January to December 2024: post engagement rate of 8,44% and post impressions of 1 454.

The AspirE project’s X account is currently experiencing modest engagement, with a post engagement rate of 8,44% and post impressions totalling 1 454. These numbers, while reflective of some visibility, suggest a few factors may contribute to the low engagement. Firstly, the project’s niche focus on migration research may limit its reach to a broader audience, as only those with specific interests in this area will likely interact with the posts. Additionally, very few team members have an X account and are active, which lessens the likeliness to retweet some relevant posts. To improve these metrics, a more targeted outreach strategy, increased use of pertinent hashtags, and engagement with key influencers and partner organisations would help boost visibility and interaction rates.

FACEBOOK

AspirE’s Facebook account was launched in the end of June 2023 and immediately has become active with a series of posts presenting the team members, the advisors, external collaborators, and the study cases. Based on the tailored publication calendar, between 2 and 3 posts are shared weekly, in coordination with publications on X.

Figure 8. Number of likes and followers on Facebook (19/12/2024)

Facebook offers detailed analytics through the Meta Business Suite, providing insights into the performance of content shared on the platform. The numbers shared cover the period of January to December 2024. As shown in Figure 9, the cumulated performance number represents an estimate of how often the content shared on AspirE’s Facebook page has been viewed. This includes visibility from users who visited the page directly and from those who came across the content through other channels. These can include sharing by different pages, platforms, or websites, increasing the reach of AspirE’s content beyond its immediate followers. This broader visibility helps assess the overall exposure of the project’s posts and their ability to circulate across different networks.

Figure 9. Cumulated coverage performance on Facebook (19/12/2024)

On the other hand, the number of visits, as illustrated in Figure 10, refers to the approximate count of times users directly accessed AspirE’s Facebook page from the launch of the Facebook page until the date indicated in the figure (19/12/2024). This metric specifically measures the traffic driven to the page itself, giving a clearer picture of how many people are actively engaging with the project’s profile. These visits are tracked when users click on the page itself, either through organic search results, direct links, or other interactions, indicating a more deliberate interest in

the project's updates and content. Together, these statistics offer a comprehensive view of both the reach and the direct engagement of the AspirE project's social media presence.

Figure 10. Approximate number of visits on Facebook (19/12/2024)

3.4. Newsletter

Since September 2023, AspirE has set up a bimonthly newsletter through Brevo (a free email newsletter software formerly Sendinblue). As of December 2024, 8 newsletters have been sent via email to an increasing number of subscribers.

According to Brevo's statistics, the open rate percentage (percentage of successfully delivered campaigns that registered as open) is 56,4%, and the click rate ((percentage of successfully delivered campaigns that registered a click) is 13,6%. It is important to note that these are only approximate numbers concerning recipients who have not enabled email privacy features. Currently, with 81 subscribers, AspirE aims to increase its visibility and subscription audience through its social media platforms, reminding followers of the existence of its bimonthly newsletter.

3.5. Partner communication channels and others

In order to further disseminate AspirE's findings and activities, team members are encouraged to reach out to their respective institutional communication channels. Some partners managed to feature the project on an institutional website, others use their active social media accounts (mostly Facebook) to share AspirE-related content.

Each team is responsible to make sure their institution valorise AspirE's findings, especially local-level outcomes and in the local language in order to reach out relevant stakeholders and overall audience. The ULB, as project coordinator, ensure to have an overview of AspirE's presence on partners' communication channels, including channels outside of the AspirE consortium (see Annex 3).

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the AspirE project's dissemination strategies, as outlined in its CD&E Plan and further analysed in this report, reflect a strong commitment to engaging both academic and non-academic audiences through a variety of channels. By leveraging social media platforms (X and Facebook), organising and attending events with international institutions and projects, AspirE has worked to increase visibility, foster interactions, and share key findings with a global audience. Despite current challenges in audience engagement, these strategies have laid the groundwork for wider outreach and provided valuable insights into content reach and interaction. The combination of detailed content planning, regular posting, and targeted promotion ensures that AspirE's research reaches key stakeholders and contributes to ongoing discussions about migration policy. Moving forward, these strategies will continue to evolve, with any necessary adjustments aimed at maximising the project's impact on social, scientific, and political levels. The final evaluation of the dissemination plan will provide valuable lessons on the effectiveness of these efforts and guide future initiatives in the field.

The AspirE project is committed to advancing human-centered approaches in the study of migration decision-making. By keeping both academic and non-academic audiences informed, the project aims to engage the broader public in discussions around migration-related matters. The third and last report on the impact of dissemination strategies will provide an overview of the impact of AspirE's online presence and activities in December 2025.

ANNEX 1 – Webinar 1 poster

WEBINAR

ASPIRING (RE)MIGRANTS' BEHAVIOUR IN MOBILITY POLICIES

29 - 30 JANUARY 2024

IN THE FRAMEWORK
OF THE PROJECT

Photo by Krzysztof Hepner via Unsplash

29/01

Case studies: Japan, Germany, Hong Kong/China, Portugal, Belgium

Discussants: Simona Vezzoli (PACES)
Sergio Carrera (CEPS)

▶ REGISTER NOW

🕒

10:00 - 12:10 CET

30/01

Case studies: Vietnam, Czech Republic, Philippines, Italy, Thailand, Finland

Discussants: Carmen Voigt-Graf (DG INTPA)
Matthias Lücke (DYNAMIG)

▶ REGISTER NOW

For information
aspire.ulb.be

This project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the call HORIZON-CL2-2022-TRANSFORMATIONS-01-04 – Grant Agreement n°101095289

ANNEX 2 – Webinar 2 poster

WEBINAR

MICRO- AND MESO-LEVEL DRIVERS OF ASIAN (RE)MIGRATION TO THE EU

30 SEPTEMBER 2024

IN THE FRAMEWORK
OF THE PROJECT

30/09/2024

10:00 - 12:00 CET

REGISTER NOW

For information

aspire.ulb.be

This project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the call HORIZON-CL2-2022-TRANSFORMATIONS-01-04 – Grant Agreement n°101095289

ANNEX 3 – Communication channels featuring the AspirE project

Partners	Website	Social Media	Other
Université libre de Bruxelles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AspirE main website https://aspire.ulb.be • Maison des Sciences Humaines – EAST https://msh.ulb.ac.be/ • ULB podcast webpage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AspirE Facebook (@AspirE2023EUproject) • EAST Facebook • AspirE X / Twitter (@AspirE_EU_Asia) • EAST X / Twitter 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AspirE Newsletter • EAST Newsletter
Tampere University	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tampere University's website 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Finland-focused Facebook page • Institutional X / Twitter account 	
Masaryk University	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Masaryk University's website 		
University Institute of Lisbon	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Iscte website • Centre of Research and Sociology studies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutional X / Twitter account 	
Goethe University Frankfurt	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GUF website 		
Scalabrini Migration Center	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SMC website 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutional Facebook page • LinkedIn 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Linktr
Mahidol University		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research Institute for Languages and Cultures of Asia (RILCA) Facebook page 	
The Isaan Record	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Isaan Record website 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facebook page (in English and Thai) • X / Twitter account 	
Waseda University	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institute of Asian Migrations website 		
IS-VASS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IS-VASS website 		
UMIL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UMIL website 		

EU projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DYNAMIG website • PACES website • INNOVATE website 		
Others	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centre for European Policy Studies website 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CEPS X / Twitter account 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CEPS Newsletter